

Need For Changes in Legal Education and Regulations in India in the Present Changing Circumstances

Rekha¹ & D P Yadav²

1. Research Scholar, S.S.J Campus Almora, Kumaon University, Almora, Uttarakhand
2. Associate Professor, Kumaon University, Almora, Uttarakhand

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Abstract

This article aims to pave How to take legal education forward in India from its current state to greatness in the future. Changing circumstances require a shift in the way we perceive reality and how education empowers and supports us in realising our true and creative potential is well known. A system that is governed by rules and whose legitimacy derives from the constitution of India , The rule of law is in danger. A wide range of creative works experimental and innovative possibilities that exist within the restrictions are being unravelled. In highlighting the gaps in the application and prevalence of rules, this article connects with the current state of affairs and enables us to face the new challenges.

Keywords: Legal Education, Indian Regulations, Indian Present Circumstances.

Introduction

Change is the law of nature, and with time and circumstances, laws also keep changing. This article will discuss the current changes in society and the new challenges that have emerged and how they can be addressed and how we can make our legal education more successful, although even when a new context is created, it is not possible to imagine and re-invent without rejecting the status quo. Discusses the need for a review of the current law and the imperatives of this etc. In addition, a complete Understanding of Regulations, including an appreciation Policies and logic, is essential at this time for any redesign of the legal education framework. This contributes to highlighting the creative areas within the regulations. The leadership of law schools should be aware of such a study, its analysis, and the wide range of regulations it clarifies. This is especially true now because the COVID-19 pandemic has changed the circumstances in which the regulation was enacted, meaning that the latter has no real significance. In this article, an attempt has been made to explain the changes in the law before, during and after Covid-19 so that readers can be helped in understanding the changing law in the changed circumstances.

In other words, t Analysis of this article is the comparative portrait, and its analytical output is the ensuing contrasts. This dissection is followed by forward looking interpretation of the regulations. offering a Manifesto for the flexibility and change , largely framed after COVID-19, but also to some extent during it, and how to meet the challenges of today, the age of the internet. The importance of this manifesto is evident from the serious tone that is conveyed. The 2 part of article details regulators past of India's legal education system. A thorough study of history and its ontological interpretation helps to appreciate the "becoming" the legal education as demonstrated by numerous legislative acts and decisions. Ultimately, history serves as the foundation for all imaginative work. The article also addresses the legal education regulatory structure that has evolved since then under the aegis An attempt has been made to analyse the efforts being made by the University Grants Commission (UGC) and the Bar Council of India (BCI).

History of Legal Education in India

A Regulatory History of legal education in India In the early years, Indian lawyers were of a lower class - law makers - whose The minimum qualification was matriculation or in many cases even less and basic knowledge of English language. However, initially the aim of law education by the British Empire was to make the people aware of British laws, High Courts were established in Calcutta, Bombay and Madras to provide justice to the people through British law, after the creation of law there was a demand for trained lawyers having understanding of law. Due to the above, a professorship was established in Government Elphinstone College in 1855.ⁱ

This college would like to subsequently merge with the University of Bombay.ⁱⁱ The official education system in India was formed almost four years later when a Government Law Colleges was established in Bombay. This college was attached to the University of Bombay and offered courses leading till the degree of Bachelor of Laws (LLB). Law institutes were established almost simultaneously in Madras and Calcutta. by the end of the year eighteenth century there were 34 law institutes in India, with a total enrollment of 3,000 students. The central government headed by the viceroy oversaw Legal education in India was also included in the world legal field during the nineteenth and early twentieth centuries. The Indian Institutes Act, 1904 was enacted as a result of the evaluation done in 1902 by the Indian Universities Commission of the performance of Indian institutions, initiated by Lord Curzon. According to this Act, the universities of Bombay, Calcutta and Madras are now able to conferring of a title doctorates in law through their separate law faculties. The recommendations of the commission eventually resulted in a requirement for a bachelor's degree for admission to the LLB program. Additionally, they reduced the duration of the LLB program from three years to two years. Additionally, the 1902 Commission suggested that "tutorials" and "case method" should be incorporated into legal education. Except for the occasional recommendations of various education commissions and committees, Legal education remained essentially unregulated till the independence of India, despite a greater The British government and Indian educationists expressed their desire for reform 33years after the country's independence, several commissions were set up to examine the state of higher education. Two of these commissions, the Law Commission of India (1958-1959) and the University Education Commission 1948-1949 (also known as the Radhakrishnan Commission lamented of state Advocacy and development of legal education in India its standardization through regulatory action.ⁱⁱⁱ After the country's independence, several commissions were set up to examine the state of higher education. Two of these commissions, the Law Commission of India (1958-1959) and the Commission on University Education 1948-1949) lamented the state of legal education in India and advocated its standardization through regulatory action. Quick after, the Advocates Act, 1961, which established the BCI, gave it the mandate to "promote legal education and to determine the standards of such education in consultation with the universities in India.^{iv} Section 10(2)(b) of the Advocates Act, 1961 provides for the constitution of a Legal Education Committee consisting of ten members "of whom five shall be persons selected by the Council from among its members and five shall be persons co-opted by the Council who are not its members" to effectively standardise and improve the To oversee legal education and to improve it effectively and for human use, soon after its establishment, the BSE started a three-year Long B Programme on the recommendation of the Law Commission of India and the Radha Kirshan Commission. As per the recommendations made by some State Bar Councils, procedures, rules, limitations, registration, evidence, drafting and professional training were started. etiquette should be introduced and supervised by the Bar Council. According to A.N. Veeraghavan, the 1961 Act, which empowered the BCI to regulate legal education, was a progressive law as it created a standard pattern of legal education without threatening the autonomy of the university.^v The BCI established its Rules in 1965, enabling it to periodically issue directives to legal education institutions in order to establish standards for legal education.^{vi} The rules reiterate the mandate of the Legal Education Committee, which includes inspecting law schools and universities, recommending recognition of these establishments and their degrees, and approving partnerships of law colleges with universities. The Bar Council of India Trust (BCI Trust) was established in 1974 by the BCI with the goal of raising professional standards and improving legal education. The Trust is required to create schools of excellence and support To achieve this objective the Trust supports initiatives aimed at promoting

legal research, welfare of the legal profession as well as ongoing legal education for the people of India. legal aid to the disadvantaged; publication of textbooks and law reports For the student.^{vii} University Grants Commission Act, 1956 (UGC Act) gave the UGC authority to regulate legal education through section 12, which allowed the UGC to take actions for the "promotion and co-ordination of University education and for the determination and maintenance of standards of teaching, examination, and research in universities," even though the BCI was still in charge of doing so throughout the 1970s and 1980s. While UGC guidelines certified the degree programs given in the nation's law colleges, the BCI continues to set standards for legal education. In accordance to Section 22 UGC Act.^{viii}

PROVISION FOR LEGAL EDUCATION IN INDIAN CONSTITUTIONS

Article 246(1) of the Indian Constitution empowers the Parliament to exclusive power to make laws with respect to any matter listed in List I (the "Union List") in the Seventh Schedule." Thus, the schools "initially known" Banaras Hindu University, Aligarh Muslim University, Delhi University which are mentioned in the Indian Constitution "any other institution declared by Parliament by law to be an institution of national importance", fall Under Article 246(1) when they are listed as Entry 63 of List I. Entry 64 further extends the Central Government's Power to make laws in relation to institutions "for scientific or technical education financed wholly or substantially by the Government of India and declared by Parliament by law to be an institution of national importance". No National Law College or Only Law College has received the designation of "institution of national importance" (INI), which is granted to institutions. in India by an Act of Parliament. "Coordination and determination of standards in institutions of higher education or research and scientific and technological" is a new Entry 66 that expands Parliament's power to pass laws. According to Entry 6, the Advocates' Association and University Grants Commission by which the Bar Council of India was created. are examples of Acts arising from Parliament's law-making jurisdiction. The federal government of India is entrusted with the task of institutionalizing and regulating higher education according to the Constitution. In fact, the central government derives this authority through Rule 2 of Article 77(3) of the Indian Constitution and the Government of India (Allocation of Business) Rules, 1961, which deals with delegation of executive authority. According to Rule 2, the "functions of the Government of India shall be performed in the Ministries, Departments, Secretariats and Offices specified in the First Schedule to these Rules." As a result, human resource development ministry (MHRD) is in charge the formulating policies and guidelines related to Higher education in India includes law education as well^{ix}

State governments have some responsibility in governing higher education, even though the federal government still retains control over higher education. On the other hand, there is some ambiguity about this. Apart from being included Higher education is included in the Union List of the Constitution under Entry 11 of the State List of the Constitution stated: "Education, including universities, subject to the provisions of Entries 63, 64, 65 and 66 of List I and Entry 25 of List III." This lack of clarity is particularly worrying in this light. Later, the Constitution (Forty-second Amendment) Act, 1976 deleted Entry 11. The deleted sentence was moved to Entry 25 of the Concurrent List (List III), which stated, "Vocational and technical training of labour, including technical education, medical education and universities, subject to the provisions of Entries 63, 64, 65 and 66 of List I." The 42nd Constitutional Amendment, 1976 made higher education a responsibility of both the Union Government and the States. As a result of these constitutional amendments, higher education is the responsibility of both the Union Government and the States. Universities are established in the States by the State Legislature. Most colleges in India are established by state legislation. For example, the National Law School of India Act, 1986 passed by the Karnataka State Legislature established the NLSIU. For example, the National Law School of India Act, 1986 passed by the Karnataka State Legislature established the NLSIU, and the National Academy of Legal Studies and Research University Act, 1998 passed by the Andhra Pradesh Legislature established the National Academy of Legal Studies and Research University and the West Bengal National University of Juridical Sciences (WBNUSU). The Karnataka State Legislature enacted the Karnataka

State Law University Act, 2009 which established the NLSIU in addition to the NLSIU. Section 3 of the University Grants Commission Act, 1956 empowers an institution to be designated as a Grants Commission. "deemed university". For all regulatory purposes, Only such a college will be considered a university. In India, the Indian Law Institute (ILI) was established in 1956 under the Societies Registration Act, 1860 with the objective of advancing legal research and training., has been designated as a deemed university by the UGC in 2005 as a result of Section 3. The UGC is important in bridging the gap between the federal government and the state in issues relating to Higher education The UGC (Establishment and Maintenance of Schools in Private Universities) Regulations, 2003 were made exercising the powers under Section 26(1)(g) and (g) of the UGC Act, 1956. Section 3(1) of the Act provides that "Every private university shall be established by a separate State act and shall conform to the relevant provisions of the UGC Act, 1956.

Public and private colleges are often empowered by state Acts to make laws and/or ordinances for their own governance. Universities are permitted to make bye-laws, subsidiary laws and internal governance policies under Section 132 I Ordinances. Article 14 of the Indian Constitution establishes that education is a fundamental right, which forms the basis of the regulatory framework for legal education in India, as it does for the entire educational system of the country. The regulatory system on education, particularly the regulatory framework on legal education, has a very important role in the constitutional rights and ideals. Legal education is a social production process because the regulatory framework for it is enshrined in the Indian Constitution, which also gives it the quality of rule of law. Re-emphasizing this,

According to A. Lakshminath, "law, legal education, and development have become interrelated concepts in modern developing countries that are struggling to develop as social welfare states and trying to improve the socio-economic conditions of the people through peaceful means." As a result, the regulatory framework establishes a legal education "ecosystem" that has the characteristics of socio-politics, including flexibility, change, and order.

2008 Rules on Legal Education Issued by the Bar Council of India

A triangular regulatory structure consisting of the applicable regulations of the UGC, the BCI, and the university to which the law school or college belongs governs legal education in India. The colleges affiliated to this institution offer law degree programmes. Of the three organisations, the BCI is primarily in charge of setting requirements for legal education and legal degree validation. The Advocates Act, 1961, Section 7(h) entrusts the BCI with the duty to "promote legal education and to determine the standards of such education in consultation with the State Bar Councils and the universities imparting such education in India". To discharge this entrusted responsibility, the BCI is authorised under Section 7(i) of the Act to recognise universities whose law degrees qualify them to be enrolled as advocates, and for this reason, to visit and inspect universities, or direct State Bar Councils to visit and inspect universities in compliance with any directions it may give in this regard. The regulatory authority of the BCI has not been free from criticism; Academics have questioned the competence of the BCI and it has faced criticism from courts and educational commissions over its mandate. The Supreme Court of India ruled that the BCI is not permitted to exercise its authority under Sections 7(h) and 7(i) of the Advocates Act to impose regulation on its own in response to challenges to the organisation's mission with regard to legal education. Instead, it must consult with the state bar councils and Indian universities, and the above consultations should be fruitful as universities are involved in providing legal education.^x However, the Court did not overturn the BCI's authority to set standards for legal education. As the Supreme Court stated in *V. Sudhir v. Bar Council of India and Others*, "We hope and trust that at least now the Bar Council of India will do well to take these suggestions [recommendations of the Academic Reforms Committees] as well as the observations made by us so as to save the standing of the entire legal profession in India." The BCI should raise standards for legal education and post-qualification training of lawyers. Despite significant concerns about its authority and competence, the BCI still regulates undergraduate and graduate legal education.^{xi}

Credibility Of Degrees And Bar Eligibility

According to the BCI Rules on Legal Education, 2008, all Indian educational establishments that offer legal teaching, including universities and law colleges connected to universities, must be approved and listed by the BCI.^{xii}

The State Bar Council is the sole body that registers advocates. Rule 37 further allows foreign university graduates with a law degree (listed under Rule 38 and recognized by the BCI through the recognition test mentioned in Rules 39 and 40) to register with the State Bar Council, provided that the graduate has reached the age of 21 years and has studied law for at least three years after graduation from any subject or five years after successful completion of the Higher Secondary School Examination. Additionally, the foreign university concerned must be an institution recognized by the BCI. Further, the BCI mandates that foreign degree holders pass "exams conducted by the Procedural Law Courses", which are required by the Bar Council of India to practice law in India.^{xiii}

ADMISSION TO LAW SCHOOL

Three-year and five-year legal education programs have been approved by the BCI for use in Indian educational institutions. A candidate for the three-year law program can be any person who has "acquired a bachelor's degree in any field from a university established by an Act of Parliament or a State Legislature or an equivalent national institution recognized as a Deemed to be University or a foreign university recognized as equivalent in status to an Indian University by the authority competent to declare equivalence." With regard to the five-year law degree program, every person who has completed senior secondary school can apply for the position.^{xiv}

Students are admitted to law schools through various means, even though the BCI sets only minimum requirements for law programmes, such as the minimum eligibility score (which is not less than 40% for "Scheduled Tribe" and "Scheduled Caste" applicants and not less than 45% for "General" category students). The Common Law Admission Test (CLAT) is the most popular and widely used test, used by most national law schools. Through the CLAT Consortium, participating National Law Universities oversee CLAT. Vice Chancellors of member National Law Schools serve as representatives on the Executive Committee and Core Committee in the Consortium. Private universities may sign a Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) with the CLAT Consortium if they are interested in admitting students through CLAT. The Punjab and Haryana High Court ruled in *Tejaswi Rana vs Punjab Institute and Ors* that the BCI's law prohibiting lateral entry and exit will take precedence over the rules of any In *Vandana Kandhari v. University of Delhi*, the Delhi High Court considered the rationale behind the minimum attendance standard prescribed by the BCI and held that while teaching legal education, students must distinguish between "acquiring an education" and "obtaining a degree".^{xv}

New challenges emerged during Covid-19 Even if Covid-19 was not there when it first emerged, it is also true that Lessons learned during the 2019 pandemic will undoubtedly have a more Positive impact on people cognition or behaviour than memories. It is true that pandemic like Covid 19 is one of the biggest pandemics most unusual events in contemporary social history - will go down in history as one of The most rigorous reality check on the condition of people. Higher education is a collective and individual effort of Easter. education Institute and regulatory agencies kept the system afloat, the pandemic left the Indian higher education industry in a state of chaos. Law college is like any other college education Institute, had stopped Physical Class when pandemic struck to prevent COVID-19 from spreading like wildfire. Many law schools then scheduled online classes, some of them immediately and some after a break of preparation. Transitioning to online education is easier said than done. Even many disadvantaged law schools were unable to accomplish this. This includes procuring the necessary software, teaching the teaching staff, Student and faculty use of online classes resources, make available the necessary support to faculty members to rethink their course content and teaching methodology, redesigning the methods and patterns of assessment and evaluation Setting it up basically for the physical class, making sure that there is a policy framework in place to

accommodate the new life that doesn't violate the rules and regulations and ensures the most important things mental health of the staff, students and faculty.

Conducting law entrance exam programs at many law colleges also became difficult as doing so in person could have put students' health and safety at risk. Due to this concern, The CLAT exam was to be held in 2020 rescheduled multiple times, while many Law School Yet some quarters have responded in a novel way. For instance, "to ensure fairness and integrity in law school admissions that advance access and equity in legal education," LSAC switched from computer based education system which is a distance education system conducted, AI Product (Artificial Intelligence) test known as "LSAT-Flex." This change was prompted by the Public emergency in the time of Covid-19. Students and institutions found that LSAT-Flex provided a seamless way to go Through admissions Helping to resolve process delays they faced Law College Admission Process.

Regulatory Challenges Before The Bar Council Of India And Universities

The first guidelines gave universities the freedom to create "MCQ/OMR-based exams, open book exams, open choice, assignment/presentation-based assessments" as alternatives to timed exams. When situations become unpredictable and volatile, stakeholders and academic institutions, including law schools, consider UGC as the only source of direction. Therefore, neither the Supreme Court nor the UGC need to support the regulatory supremacy of the UGC. To achieve the best results that are still efficient, it is now necessary to understand the expectations of stakeholders, recognize that the concept of "normal" has been lost, and rethink norms. The National Education Policy 2020, made public in September 2020 amid the pandemic, responded to the above situation by stating that "the regulatory system needs a comprehensive overhaul to promote and prosper the higher education sector." According to the policy, the rules should be "light but strict."^{xvi}

Agenda For Regulation In Legal Education

As the pandemic changed the landscape, the regulatory structure that was in place - which set norms for law school governance and defined standards for legal education - became more restrictive. Not only did laws affect various areas, but the concept of the rule of law also became problematic due to the changed circumstances, casting doubts on the legitimacy and competence of our governmental institutions. However, this does not indicate any flaw in

regulation or the rule of law. Regulation is not the same as the rule of law, which is the Despite so many difficulties, there is hope for rebuilding the world after Covid-19. ^{xvii}

Online socialization, including online learning, has become a new reality and a form If this is a social product then how is it online socialization differ basically in-person socialization? Online space is therefore the extent of one's being in physical space rather than a simulated replication of physical space. The subject's simple desire to explore specific additional spaces is what initiates such an extension.

This conflicts with the BCI's mandatory attendance requirement for law students because neither the law school nor the students can be in class at the same time and verify that Found the Sudentu gets instructions In light of this situation, Many law colleges have given relaxation in their attendance. requirements the eliminating penalties for absenteeism. Although law schools may take such steps to help students, they also place greater The student is responsible for watching live or recorded classes, reading transcripts, and studying the law and obtaining the necessary training to meet legal requirements. This goes against the BCI's mandatory attendance requirement for law students because neither the law school nor the students can be in class at the same time and verify that The student got required Instruction. In light of situation, Many law colleges have given relief in attendance requirements by, eliminating penalties for absenteeism. Although law schools may take such steps to help students, they also place greater Responsibility of watching live on the student or recorded Class recording, read transcripts, and receive the necessary training to meeting the standards of the law and education. The concept of "apprenticeship" can be generated through Via Compute communications between teacher and student. It may be qualitatively correlated to the student-teacher relationship to a large extent.

Among other things, the pandemic has changed the environment in which teaching is conducted in classrooms. Distance learning does not fall under the traditional teaching-learning framework used at the College of Law, as in India Online education has always been governed by the UGC Regulations 2018. The regulatory environment that existed before the pandemic inevitably reflects how deeply embedded The practice of discussion was prevalent in the law college, hence these things should be kept in mind before making any preconceived idea. close relationship that exists between teaching and discursive practices. Therefore, it may be wiser to examine options within the current restrictions rather than rushing all-in. A "flexible" strategy would be best as it would provide decision-makers with more "space" for all possible pandemic-related contingencies. Through application in new contexts Freshness of ideas ranging from the concept of law college to the scope of placement of students in an uncertain industry environment must be put into context. Hence, in legal education, becomes imagination driving power in thoughts take on New meanings as imitation challenges reconstruction.

New Rules For Bar Council Of India (2024)

On 20 May 2024, a guideline has been issued by the bar council of india, which states that it will be The law should be mandatory for all colleges to comply with it. It is known that a new education policy has been implemented in 2020 but legal education was kept out of it. That is why this guideline has been issued by the Bar Council of India which is as follows :Reminder Regarding Emerging Subjects' Inclusion:

- I. The importance of constitutional values is emphasized
- II. Setting in Context with Socioeconomic and Cultural Facts
- III. Education in Two Languages for Accessible Justice
- IV. Encouragement of Multidisciplinary and Critical Thinking
- V. Mandatory Inclusion of Mediation in Legal Education: Executive and Judicial Order
- VI. Integration of Computer Education into Legal Education: Implementation Directive and Compliance
- VII. Including Recently Passed Laws in University Curriculum
- VIII. The BCI has not approved or recognized law courses offered online, through correspondence, open, or distance learning under the titles LL.B.2, BA (Law, etc.); LL.M., MA (Law, etc.), etc.
- IX. Timetable for general class/course conduct by CLEs
- X. Guidelines and Requirements for bar council of India Regulations on the Equivalency of Foreign Law Degrees and Compliance with Indian Legal Education Rules
- XI. Regular Evaluation and Modification:
- XII. Compliance with the Sanctioned Seat Strength in Law Centers: Any reservations or quotas must stay within the sanctioned seat strength and not go beyond it. The BCI will only accept degrees granted to students who occupy the authorized number of seats.
- XIII. Execution and Adherence to Compliance.

Conclusion

As mentioned earlier, Legal education in India is a cosmopolitan system. based on the vision of the rule of Law and as such, it plays a role in the entire social production as well as the progressive development of society. Indian legal education was able to withstand Challenges presented covid-19 pandemic thanks to the country's strong legal system as well as the laws and regulations Governing the sector. But while society appreciated the importance of the rule of law in terms of ensuring citizens' Justice till justice, combating inequality, and protecting their physical and mental health, regulatory bodies relied on the ability of rules to increase adaptability and flexibility to guarantee change. The pandemic has also been educational in many ways, giving us a chance to better understand the potential of technology in education, whether in the form of remotely connected asynchronous classes or AI-proctored, home-based entrance exams. The interesting thing about all this is that in today's environment where today's era is becoming the era of technology, new crimes are being born, it is the era of internet, so there is a need to include the laws related to this new

technology in law education so that the upcoming lawyers and judges who ensure the reach of justice in the society can develop an understanding of those crimes and laws, the rule of Indian laws and constitutional as the most successful strategy to advance and maintain legal education in India.

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